

Towards Systematic Specification and Verification of Fairness Requirements: A Position Paper

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Software became responsible for sensitive decisions with far-reaching societal impacts.

Risk: falsely developed software may lead to unlawful discrimination against persons.

COMPAS

<https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing>

In 2016, discriminated between crimes offenders on the basis of their ethnicity.

<https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2016-amazon-same-day/>

In 2016, indirectly discriminated between customers on the basis of their ethnicity.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

GDPR imposed restrictions on decision making based on special category of data (Protected characteristics).

Fairness in AI software development

a) Mitigating discrimination

b) Detecting discrimination

Mapping the literature to SDLS

Mapping the literature to SDLS

Existing approaches for analyzing software fairness focus on *ex-post* analysis. These methods rely on hard-coded constraints, limiting their ability to address fairness issues proactively

Objectives

Our collective responsibility is to ensure fairness in AI systems from the onset of system development. To achieve this goal we aim at:

- **Obj1.** Empowering requirements engineers with an approach that enable them in formulating *unambiguous* and *verifiable* fairness requirements.
- **Obj2.** Developing an approach that *systematically* verifies compliance with fairness requirements during the *design* and *implementation* phases of the system.

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Realizing these two objectives is a challenging task!

Challenges

Challenge 1. It is unclear which aspects have to be covered for specifying unambiguous and verifiable fairness requirements

- Data subject to be protected
- Fairness measure to be applied (e.g., demographic parity, equal opportunity, predictive parity, individual fairness, etc.)
- Protected characteristics
- Proxies in specific context
- Domain knowledge + Legal knowledge
- ...

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Failure to account for these aspects and many other may lead inexperienced developers to fall into the *formalism trap*.

Challenges

Challenge 2. Only avoiding protected characteristics in decision-making software does not prevent dis-crimination. Indirect discrimination can happen due to

- Proxies (Data Correlations)
- Data flow

“fairness is not a property of software in isolation, fairness is a property of the software composed into its system” (Dwork et al., 2018).

Scenarios should be verified at system design level

Scenario 1. Data flow of protected characteristics or proxies

Scenarios should be verified at system design level

Scenario 2. Gateways/Condition control the decision making

Assume that income is a proxy for age!

This assumption introduces a potential fairness concern early in the decision process.

Challenges

Challenge 3. The GDPR generally discourages and in most cases strictly prohibits the collection and processing of sensitive personal data.

- This raises the question of how proxies (i.e., correlations with protected characteristics) can be determined?

Research questions

RQ1. How can we assist requirements engineers in specifying unambiguous and verifiable fairness requirements?

RQ2. How can fairness requirements be systematically enforced throughout the modeling and implementation of AI systems?

FairReq: Specifying fairness requirements based on an ontology

To propose a fairness requirement engineering framework that enables specifying verifiable fairness requirements

Tasks

Task1 To develop a machine-readable glossary.

Concept	Definition
Individual fairness
.....	

Task2 To develop a knowledge graph that captures the relationships between different concepts in the glossary

Objectives and Tasks

Task3 To customize requirement engineering templates (e.g., MASTER, also known as Rupp templates)

Task4 To propose a tool that uses the template to allow specifying fairness requirements in a semi-automatic way.

FairCheck: Integrating and Verifying fairness requirements

To propose a fairness requirement engineering framework that enables specifying verifiable fairness requirements

Tasks

Task1 To develop a method to automatically integrate the specified requirements checks into *software models* and *source code* by leveraging knowledge graph-driven transformations and rule-based mapping

Example: Using the customized MASTER template:

Req: “The loan approval system must ensure equal opportunity by treating applicants with similar creditworthiness equally, regardless of age or gender.”


```
def evaluate_application(application):  
    income = application.income  
    # @FairnessWarning: income may act as a proxy for AGE  
    if income > 5000:  
        result = model1.predict(application.data)  
    else:  
        result = model2.predict(application.data)  
    return result
```

Tasks

Task2 To develop system-level design-time checks. At this stage, we check fairness at the system architecture level while treating the ML component as a black box.

Example: Using linear temporal logic and model checking to Prove or disprove verification objective:

For any initialization of the attributes, the **call of ML decision making component** in any feasible path of the system **is independent from** the setting of **all protected characteristics** and proxy attributes.

Conclusion: Make fairness a shared responsibility, not an afterthought

- Discrimination isn't just a bug—it's a design flaw..
- As with security, fairness needs to be a first-class entity in the SDLC.

Proposed Roadmap